

STUDY ON MARKETING COST, MARKETING EFFICIENCY, MARKETING MARGIN, PRICE SPREAD & PRODUCER SHARE IN CONSUMER RUPEES, IN VALUE CHAIN ANALYSIS OF ROSE (Polyantha)

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Abstract:

The present study named Study on Marketing cost, marketing efficiency, marketing margin, price spread, producer share in consumer rupees, and identify the different marketing channels in value chain analysis of rose (Polyanthas) in Vizayangaram district of Andhra Pradesh. This study aims to investigate Marketing cost, and Marketing efficiency, price spread and producers share in consumer rupees of Rose (Polyanthas) in Vizayangaram district of AP. The present study was conducted on year 2021-2023. The study was conducted in Kothavalsa block of Vizayangaram district. For this study 5 villages were selected from Kothavalsa block, the study reveals there is marketing cost, marketing efficiency, marketing channels in comparatively higher.

Keywords: marketing cost, marketing efficiency, price spread, producer share in consumer rupees, marketing channels, Vizayangaram in value chain analysis of rose (Polyanthas).

Introduction:

Indian retail the sector is predominantly unorganized. However, organized retail units are fast emerging and becoming the prefer choice of consumers, especially in urban areas. The organized retail sector implies presence of large retailers, greater enforcement of taxation mechanism and better labour law monitoring system. Organized retailing of fresh produce in India took off in the post liberalization era. Due to change in consumer Demographics, the increase in families, income, urbanization, awareness and access of internet media has influenced the consumer behaviour to choose products from modern retail outlets. The success of organized retail format, any format for that matter, significantly depends on consumer's patronage. . Roses are one of the most needed and consumed items. Every household consumes vegetables on a daily basis, though some purchase them for 2-3 days because they have the luxury of the refrigerator

Objectives:

1. To work out marketing cost of rose (Polyanthas) in the market
2. To work out marketing efficiency and price spread of rose (Polyanthas) in the market
3. To evaluate Producer share in consumer rupees.

Materials and Methods**Selection of District:**

Andhra Pradesh consists of 14 districts out of this Vizayanagaram district was selected purposely for the present study on production.

Selection of Block:

To select a Kothavalsa block, a complete list of blocks was obtained from the Head Quarter of Vizayanagaram district. Out of 8 blocks, the key potential block was selected purposively for the present study.

Kothavalasa**Selection of Villages:**

A list of Rose, producing villages was prepared with the help of an extension officer, kvk, Vizayanagaram, out of which 5% of villages will be selected purposively to make our study convenient.

S.no	Name of villages	Respondents
1	Kothavalsa	45
2	Ramabhadrapuram	20
3	Gantyada	33
4	Makkuva	10
5	Anandapuram	12
Total	-	120

Selection of Respondents:

A complete list of all the respondents in the selected villages was prepared, out of which 10% of respondents was selected randomly for production

S. No	Farm group	Area(acres)
1	Small	2-4
2	Medium	6-10
3	Large	>10

Data source and Data types

Primary Data: Primary data regarding socio-economic, production aspects (the cost and returns) and marketing of rose and the problems in production and marketing etc. Is collected by interviewing them personally with the help of pretested schedule.

Secondary Data: All the necessary secondary data related to the topic is collected from various published sources like journals, bulletins, books, magazines, and particular websites, etc. And other sources of secondary data include various Government officers like the block office, Market office and District Agricultural office

Method of data analysis:**Marketing Cost:**

The total cost incurred on marketing by various intermediaries involved in the sale and purchase of the commodity till it reaches the ultimate consumer was computed as follow

Marketing cost = C - Cf + Cml + Cm2 + Cm3 +... + Cmn

Where:

C = total cost of marketing

Cf = cost born by the producer from the time produce leaves the farm till the sale of produce.

Cmn = cost incurred by middlemen in the process of buying and selling.

2. Marketing Efficiency:

Market efficiency refers to the degree to which market prices reflect all available, relevant information. If markets are efficient, then all information is already incorporated into prices, and so there is no way to "beat" the market because there are no undervalued or overvalued securities available.

MME=FP/MC+MM

Where

MME is modified measure of marketing efficiency

FP= Price received by farmers

MC= Marketing cost

MM= Marketing margin

Results and Discussion:

Table 2: Marketing Cost of Rose in different marketing channels

Particulars	Roses	
	Number of responses	Percentage Distribution
From who commission agent purchased		
Farmer	40	26.6%
Trader	30	20 %
Commission Agent	30	20 %
Cold Storage	40	26.6 %
Total	160	100.00
From who retailer purchased		
Commission Agent	150	100.00
To whom commission Agent sold		
Retailer - Trader	95	63.3 %
Commission Agent	5	3.3 %
Total	100	100.00
To whom Farmer sold		
Commission Agent	40	100
To whom retailer sold		
Retailer	10	6.6 %
Consumer	140	93.3 %
Total	150	100.00

Table.3: Marketing Efficiency Of Rose In Different Marketing CHANNELS

Particulars	Units	ChannelI	ChannelII	ChannelIII
Consumer purchase price	PerKg	656	730	720
Total marketing price		31	66	70
Total net margin of intermediaries		-	54	28
Net price received market intermediaries		625	664	650
Marketing efficiency by Conventional method		20.16%	62.8%	36.57%

Table 3. Reveals about the marketing efficiency of different marketing channels in which marketing efficiency of channel I by conventional method is 20.16%, marketing efficiency of channel II is 62.8% and marketing efficiency of channel III is 36.57%. The total

marketing price was high in channel II in comparison of other channels. The maximum net margin received by market intermediaries is highest in Channel II i.e. 54.

Channel 1

S. No	Particulars	Price/Kg
1	Net price received by producer	625
2	Cost incurred by the producer	
a	Packing cost	10
b	Packing material cost	11
c	Miscellaneous charges	10
3	Total marketing cost	31
4	Sale price of producer/Purchase price of Consumer	656
	Price spread	31
	Producer's share in consumer rupee	95.89%

Table 1: Price Spread Of Rose In Channel I

Channel-II:

Table 2: Price Spread Of Rose In Channel II

S. No	Particulars	Price/Kg
1	Net price received by producer	585
2	Cost incurred by the producer	
a	Packing cost	10
b	Packing material cost	11
c	Miscellaneous charges	20
3	Marketing cost	41
4	Sale price of producer/Purchase price of Commission agent	626
5	Cost incurred by the Commission agent	
	Margin of commission agent	30

6	Sale price of Commission agent/ purchase price of wholesaler	656
7	Cost incurred by the Processor	
8	Loading and unloading and repacking charges	05
9	Processing charges	20
	Margin of processor	11
	Sale price of Wholesaler/Purchase price of retailer	692
	Handling Charges	10
	Carriage up to shop	05
	Miscellaneous charges	10
	Marketing cost	25
	Margin of Retailer	13
11	Sale price of retailer/purchase price of consumer	730
	Total Marketing Cost	66
	Net Margin	54
	Price Spread	145
	Producers share in consumer rupee	80.13

Channel III:**Table 3. Price Spread Of Rose In Channel Iii**

1	Net price received by producer	600
2	Cost incurred by the producer	
a	Packing cost	10
b	Packing material cost	15
c	Miscellaneous charges	20
3	Marketing cost	45
	Sale price of Producer/ Purchase price of processor	645
7	Cost incurred by the Processor	
9	Processing charges	20
	Packaging charges	12
	Margin of processor	18
	Sale price of Processor/Purchase price of retailer	685
	Handling Charges	10
	Carriage up to shop	05
	Miscellaneous charges	10
	Marketing cost	25
	Margin of Retailer	10
11	Sale price of retailer/ Purchase price of consumer	720
	Total Marketing cost	70
	Net margin	28
	Price Spread	120
	Producer's share in consumer rupee	83.33

Table 3: Producer's share in consumer rupees of rose in market:

s.no	Rose	Kothavalasa	Ramabhadrapuram	Gantiyada	Makkuva	Anandapuram
1	Polyanthas	31.9	46.7	29.3	38.6	45.5
2	Climbing	28.2	40.0	29.0	34.6	46.2
3	Beach rose	54.1	60.0	72.7	70.6	72.5
4	French rose	53.3	41.2	47.4	69.0	57.1
	Average	43.4	47.5	46.4	53.3	57.7

Conclusion:

It may be concluded from the study that there is an immense scope for expansion of area and production of rose in Chaka as well as in other suitable part of Vizayanagaram district. The cost of cultivation of rose is higher but due to good demand in market, the return are also very good. Producers can get a net profit on marketing of rose through channel 1 is Rs.40 and Rs.32, channel -2 and channel 3 Rs.36, Rs. 26 respectively

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